

**DEVELOPMENT OF THERMOSENSITIVE IN SITU GELS FOR
OPHTHALMIC DRUGS DELIVERY****Maushmi Thakur*¹, Rajaram R. Rajbhar*², Mr. Gopal Kumar³**

¹B. Pharmacy VIII- Semester Students, Aryabhata Knowledge University, A and E College of Pharmacy Samastipur, Bihar.

²Assistant Professor (Head of Department), Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, A and E College of Pharmacy, Mohiuddin Nagar, Samastipur, Bihar.

³Assistant Professor, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, A and E College of Pharmacy, Mohiuddin Nagar, Samastipur, Bihar.

Article Received on
09 August 2025,

Revised on 30 August 2025,
Accepted on 19 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17213640>

***Corresponding Author**

Maushmi Thakur

B. Pharmacy VIII- Semester
Students, Aryabhata
Knowledge University, A
and E College of Pharmacy
Samastipur, Bihar.

ABSTRACT

This study endeavored to overcome the physiological barriers hindering optimal bioavailability in ophthalmic therapeutics by devising drug delivery platforms that allow therapeutically effective drug concentrations in ocular tissues for prolonged times. Thermosensitive drug delivery platforms were formulated by blending poloxamers (F68 and F127) with low-molecular-weight hyaluronic acid (HA) in various concentrations and loaded with hydrocortisone (HC). The temperature sensitive in situ gel formulations, undergo phase transition from liquid to semisolid gel upon exposure to physiological eye temperature. These are free-flowing liquid at room temperature and easy to administer into the eye as drops. They undergo in situ phase transition to form a strong gel that is capable of withstanding shear forces in the culde-sac and of sustaining drug release at physiological conditions. The aim of the present study was

the development of thermo-sensitive *in-situ* gels for *in-vitro* evaluation of ophthalmic delivery systems of ketorolac tromethamine (KT), based on methylcellulose (MC) in combination with hydroxypropylmethyl cellulose (HPMC). The gel temperature of 1% MC solution was observed at 60°C. It was found that 6% oral rehydration salt without dextrose (ORS) was capable to reduce the gel temperature below physiological temperature. HPMC was added to increase viscosity and drug release time.

KEYWORDS: Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, ORS, Gelling capacity, in situ gel, in vitro diffusion study, Lomefloxacin, Pluronic F127, Thermo-reversible sol gel, Cold technique, Phase transition, Shear thinning systems, Methylcellulose.

1. INTRODUCTION

Major problem in ocular therapeutics is the attainment of optimal drug concentration at the site of action, which is comprised mainly due to precorneal loss resulting in only a small fraction of the drug being ocularly absorbed. The effective dose administered may be altered by increasing the retention time of medication into the eye by using in situ gel-forming systems. Ophthalmic drug delivery is an extremely interesting and highly challenging endeavor.^[1,2] The anatomy, physiology, and biochemistry of the eye render this organ exquisitely impervious to foreign substances. The challenge to the formulator is to circumvent the protective barriers of the eye without causing permanent tissue damage.^[3] Major disadvantage of ointment, providing blurred vision, due to this it could be used either night time or for treatment on the outside and edges of the eyelids. Suspension as ophthalmic delivery systems relies on the assumption that particles may persist in conjunctival sac. Precorneal drug loss can be minimal, such as retarding drainage by using diffusion-controlled, nonerodible polymeric insert. The major disadvantage of inserts is the lack of patient acceptance owing to difficult administration.^[4] The conventional liquid ophthalmic formulations are washed out from the precorneal area immediately upon instillation because of constant lacrimal secretion, nasolacrimal drainage and short precorneal residence time of the solution.^[5] As a result, frequent instillation of solution or higher drug concentration is needed to achieve the desired therapeutic response.^[6,7] but this attempt is potentially dangerous if drug solution drained from the eye is systemically absorbed from the nasolacrimal duct.^[8] To increase precorneal residence time and ocular bioavailability, different ophthalmic delivery systems such as viscous solutions, ointments, gels, suspensions or polymeric inserts are used.^[9] But because of blurred vision (e.g. ointments) or lack of patient compliance (e.g. inserts), these formulations have not been widely accepted. This problem can be overcome by using *in-situ* gel forming ocular drug delivery system, prepared from polymer, exhibit sol-to-gel phase transition due to a change in a specific physico-chemical parameter (pH, temperature, etc.) in their environment.^[10] and as a result, sustained drug release to the eye occurs.^[11] Such formulations were used to delivered bioactive agents by instillation into the eye, which upon exposure to the eye temperature changes to the gel phase.^[12] Thus, precorneal residence time of the delivery system is increased and ocular

bioavailability is also enhanced. MC solution is known to undergo thermos-reversible sol-to-gel transition. Gel temperature of MC can be reduced by adding salts and other additives.^[13] The eye presents unique challenges in terms of its anatomical and physiological nature, as well as its defense mechanisms, thus rendering drug delivery to ocular tissues a cumbersome task due to issues associated with bioavailability. Topical instillation of drugs via eye drops is the primary route of administration for the treatment of various ocular disorders affecting the anterior segment of the eye, including dry eye disease, conjunctivitis, uveitis, diabetic macular oedema and postoperative inflammation.^[14] However, conventional pharmaceutical formulations, such as solutions and suspensions, have many drawbacks. These include rapid precorneal elimination, gravity drainage, normal tear turnover, enzymatic metabolism, nasolacrimal drainage, conjunctival absorption, and lack of controlled release and bioadhesive properties.^[15] The limited permeability of the ocular membranes also contributes to the low absorption of the drugs, determining the short duration of the therapeutic effect and making a frequent dosing regimen necessary. On the other hand, the instillation of highly concentrated eye drops can cause adverse effects and cellular damage to eye tissues.^[16]

2. Classification of in situ gel

1) Based on physical stimuli

- a) Thermally Triggered System
- b) pH Triggered System

2) Based on physical mechanism

- a) Swelling
- b) Diffusion

3) Based on chemical reaction

- a) Ion cross linking
- b) Enzymatic cross linking
- c) Photo polymerization

2.1 In-vitro gelation studies

The gel temperature of 1% MC solution is 60°C. The effect of ORS on gel temperature of MC solution has been shown in figure 2. The gel temperature is reduced below body temperature by addition of ORS. The addition of salt will affect the structure of water, which is mainly due to the interactions between ions and water molecules. Salting out salts of ORS

stronger interact with water than hydrogen bonds between water molecules. As a result, the hydrogen bonds between water molecules are destroyed by the salt.^[17] Salt ions also attract more water molecules due to their stronger hydration abilities than MC chains. This effect decreases water-solubility of MC. In this situation formation of hydrophobic aggregates are more pronounced in a salt containing MC solution. The increased salt content results in fewer free water molecules around MC chains and a stronger hydrophobic environment for MC. So the sol-gel transition occurs at a lower temperature. It has been observed that 6% ORS is capable to ensure a gelation temperature below body temperature and the solutions are free flowing liquid to allow reproducible instillation into the eye as drops at room temperature. HPMC does not significantly alter the gel temperature. All the developed formulations were evaluated for clarity by visual inspection and clarity was sufficient.

2.2 Ocular irritancy

Ocular irritation study was performed on optimized formulation in four albino rabbits (male), each weighing about 2 to 3 kg, and 0.1 ml of the optimized sterile moxifloxacin hydrochloride formulation was instilled in to cul-de-sac twice a day for a period of 14 days. The rabbits were monitored periodically for redness, swelling, watering of the eye.

2.3 In vitro drug release of In situ gel system

In vitro release studies of the formulations were studied through a fabricated apparatus consisting of 1 ml of formulation placed in donor compartment using cello phane membrane (molecular weight cutoff 12,000 14,000 Dalton) which was soaked for 24 h in STF. The donor compartment was immersed in the receptor compartment containing 50 ml of STF maintained at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ with constant stirring using magnetic stirrer. After regular time intervals, 1 ml was withdrawn from receiver compartment and replaced with fresh STF. All samples were withdrawn in triplicates. Samples were analyzed for amount of drug released with UV-spectro photometer at 280 nm against STF pH 7.4 as blank.^[18]

2.4 Rheological studies

Viscosity of the formulation was determined before and after gelation by using Brookfield's rheometer. (DV II+USA) using spindle number 21. Formulations were taken in a small volume sample tube and viscosity was measured at 5, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 rpm. Thermo stated water jacket was used in order to measure viscosity at $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at $37 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The viscosity was measured before dilution with STF at $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2$ and before and after dilution with STF at $37 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.^[19]

2.5 Preparation of in situ gel

The polymeric solution was prepared by dispersing required quantity of sodium alginate as main polymer and HPMC- E 50 LV, HPMC- K4M as co-polymers in water using a magnetic stirrer until the polymers completely dissolve. Aqueous solution of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was added in to the polymeric solution with continuous stirring.^[20] Buffering and osmolality agents were added to the resulting solution along with benzalkonium chloride. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.5 using 0.1 N NaOH/0.1 N HCl.

2.6 Gelling capacity

The gelling capacity of the prepared formulation was determined by placing a drop of the formulation in a vial containing 2 ml of freshly prepared simulated tear fluid and visually observed. The time taken for its gelling was noted.^[21,22]

3. EVALUATION OF AN IN-SITU GEL

3.1 Clarity & pH

Clarity is one of most essential parameter for ophthalmic preparations. All prepared formulations were evaluated for clarity by visual observation against black and white background and pH was determined using digital pH meter.

3.2 Drug content

Prepared in situ gel formulation (equivalent to 10 mg of pure drug) was taken and diluted to 100 ml with freshly prepared Simulated tear fluid (Composition: NaCl-0.67 g, NaHCO₃-0.20, CaCl₂, 2H₂O-0.008 g and distilled water to 100 ml) (STF). From this 1 ml was withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml using STF. The absorbance was measured at 280 nm against STF as blank by using UV-Visual Spectro photometer.^[23]

3.3 Gel strength

Prepared formulation 25 g was placed in 100 ml graduated cylinder and gelled at 37°C using thermostat. A 14 g weight is placed on to gelled form and allowed to penetrate 5 cm. Time required for penetration is noted and reported as the gel strength.^[24]

3.4 Gelling capacity

The gelling capacity of the in-situ gel formulations was determined by placing a drop of formulation in a test tube containing 2 ml of simulated tear fluid freshly prepared and

equilibrated at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and visually assessing the formation of gel, noting the time for gelation and the time taken for the formed gel to dissolve.^[25]

3.5 Measurement of gelation temperature (GT)

Sample solution of 10 ml was taken in a transparent beaker and placed in a water bath. The whole assembly was placed on magnetic stirrer and gradually temperature of the water bath was increased with continuous stirring at minimum rpm. The temperature at which the magnetic bar stopped moving due to gelation is noted as the gelation temperature.^[26]

3.6 Viscosity study

The viscosity of the formulations is investigated as a function of temperature. The formulations behave as liquids and exhibit low viscosity at 25°C . At 37°C , the solutions are converted into gels with high viscosity. The reasons for this increase in viscosity are that the polymers are fully hydrated and simple entanglement exists between polymer chains at low temperature. The hydration of polymer by water is gradually weakened when the temperature increases, the hydrophobic association of polymer becomes more pronounced and a gel structure is formed. It has been observed that the viscosity enhancing capability of HPMC is much higher than MC alone.

4. PREPARATION OF *IN SITU* GEL

The polymeric solution was prepared by dispersing required quantity of sodium alginate as main polymer and HPMC- E 50 LV, HPMC- K4M as co-polymers in water using a magnetic stirrer until the polymers completely dissolve. Aqueous solution of moxifloxacin hydrochloride was added in to the polymeric solution with continuous stirring.^[27] Buffering and osmolality agents were added to the resulting solution along with benzalkonium chloride. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.5 using 0.1 N NaOH/0.1 N HCl. The *in situ* gel formulations are depicted in Table 1.

4.1 Physical parameters

The formulated *in situ* gel solution was tested for clarity, pH, gelling capacity, and drug content estimation. The results are as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Evaluation parameters of formulations.

Formulations	Visual appearance	Clarity	pH	Drug content	Gelling capacity
F1	Transparent	Clear	6.51	98.68	++
F2	Transparent	Clear	6.53	93.41	++
F3	Transparent	Clear	6.51	96.84	++
F4	Transparent	Clear	6.49	94.29	++
F5	Transparent	Clear	6.53	99.24	++
F6	Transparent	Clear	6.53	93.81	++

++: Gelation immediate remains for few hours.

4.2 Gelling capacity

The gelling capacity of the prepared formulation was determined by placing a drop of the formulation in a vial containing 2 ml of freshly prepared simulated tear fluid and visually observed. The time taken for its gelling was noted.^[28,29]

4.3 Rheological studies

The viscosity measurements were carried out using Brookfield viscometer LVDV-E model. The *in situ* gel formulations were placed in the sampler tube. The samples were analyzed at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ by a circulating bath connected to the viscometer adaptor prior to each measurement. The angular velocity of the spindle was increased 1 to 4 and the viscosity of the formulation was measured.^[30,31] Rheological evaluation of all the formulation exhibited Newtonian flow before gelling and exhibited pseudoplastic flow after gelling in the eye. There was increase in the viscosity after gelling. Additionally, the gel formed *in situ* should maintain its integrity without dissolving or eroding for a prolonged period.

In situ forming gels are the dosage forms which are liquid in nature outside the body and when they are instilled into the eye they are converted into gel upon the environmental changes like pH, temperature and upon ion activation.^[32] The formation of the gel increases the residence time in the eye which is helpful in prolonging the corneal contact time, reducing the drainage of drug thus leading to an enhanced bioavailability. These formulations will also improve patient compliance by reducing the frequency of administration.^[33]

5. ADVANTAGE OF *IN SITU* FORMING GELS

- Mainly used to maintain for the prolonged and controlled release of the drug from the formulation.
- The formation of gel mainly increases the ocular contact time and residence time which is helpful for the enhancement of the bioavailability.

- Due to the secretion of the lacrimal fluids from the eye there will be rapid drainage of the drug which is a major drawback of the conventional dosage forms. This limitation can be overcome by the formation of gel.
- *In situ* forming gels will increase the patient compliance by reducing the frequency of administration.
- *In situ* forming gels are also helpful in the targeted drug delivery.
- Accurate dosing is possible which may not involve in the over dose and dose dumping.
- More comfortable with improved patient compliance when compared to other dosage forms like ocular inserts etc.
- Drug loss through naso-lacrimal duct is minimized as it can lead to unwanted side effects.^[34,35]
- Improved Local Bioavailability
- Reduced dose frequency
- Patient-friendly
- Prolonged drug release
- Due to gelation precorneal residence time is increased and nasolacrimal drainage is decreased.^[36]

6. DISADVANTAGES OF *IN SITU* GEL

- It necessitates a large amount of fluids.
- The drug's sol form is more sensitive to deterioration.
- Chemical deterioration could cause stability issues.
- Eating and drinking may be restricted for several hours after the medication is implanted.
- Drug loading into hydrogels may be limited in terms of amount and uniformity, especially for hydrophobic drug.
- Only medications with a low dose requirement can be administered.
- Lower mechanical strength can lead to early failure.
- The hydrogel dissolves or flows away from a specific local spot.

Ocular disorders are prevalent worldwide affecting millions of people and having a significant impact on their quality of life. A range of inflammatory, viral, and degenerative conditions can impact the eyes. These include diseases of the anterior segment like conjunctivitis, dry eye disease, keratitis, ulcers, corneal neovascularization, conical cornea,

and cystinosis^[37], as well as the back of the eye including neovascular age-related macular degeneration (AMD), diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, hereditary retinal degenerations, rod cone dystrophy, posterior uveitis, and eye tumours^[38], all leading to discomfort, disturbances in vision, visual impairment, and even loss of sight. It is estimated that there are at least 2.2 billion visual impairments worldwide, and a substantial number of these impairments could have been prevented if adequately treated^[39] Topical application is an effective route to treat several eye ailments both in terms of cost and patient convenience. It ensures local delivery avoiding systemic side effects. In the context of treating glaucoma, for example, drugs like acetazolamide and ethoxzolamide, which belong to the class of oral carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, have frequently been discontinued due to their systemic toxicity.^[40,41] The creation of a gel upon applying an aqueous solution to the eye is achieved by utilizing polymers that react to external stimuli. These systems are produced through a straightforward manufacturing process.^[42] Gel formation can be triggered by changes in pH, ions, or temperature. Thermoresponsive *in situ* gelling systems comprise polymers that remain in a liquid state below a certain temperature called the lower critical solution temperature (LCST), and above an upper critical solution temperature (UCST). When the ambient temperature reaches or surpasses the LCST, these polymers undergo gelation. Conversely, when the temperature drops below the UCST, the polymer transitions from gel to sol. Another approach to *in situ* gel creation involves incorporating polymers with acidic or basic functional groups that respond to a change in pH. In ionic systems, modifications in ionic concentration, particularly involving monovalent and/or divalent cations present in tears like Na⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ ions, facilitate the interconversion between gel and sol states.^[43] When drug products are transported through ophthalmic channels, they face physiological and structural hurdles, including efflux pumps, reflex blinking, and nasolacrimal drainage. Nanotechnology, which regulates drug release, can resolve the issue of low bioavailability caused by these obstacles.^[44] Additionally, nanotechnology may help mitigate side effects associated with conventional formulations. Nanocarriers made up of small particles may exhibit improved permeability, making them an attractive option for drug delivery. Chitosan (CS), a natural polymer with plentiful natural reserves, is frequently utilized as a nanocarrier because of its excellent characteristics, such as simple preparation, biodegradability, and good biocompatibility.^[45] The protonated amino groups in CS facilitate interaction with the DNA and RNA of fungi and bacteria, inhibiting protein synthesis and enabling it to be easily electrostatically adsorbed onto the negatively charged surfaces of microorganisms. Therefore, drugs loaded onto CS have enhanced penetration and antibacterial capabilities. In addition,

chitosan nanoparticles (CNPs) have shown enhanced efficiency in pathogen biofilm eradication compared to free (no nanocarrier) drugs, making them a promising substitute for traditional drug delivery methods.^[46,47] *In situ* gel systems are composed of polymers that can be easily administered as liquids in non-physiological environments but solidify into a semisolid gel when exposed to physiological conditions.^[48] *In situ* gels have been developed for ocular use, with recent studies reporting the preparation of mucoadhesive ocular gels delivering itraconazole nanocrystals for the treatment of fungal keratitis^[49] and a mucoadhesive *in situ* gel of Riluzole-loaded biodegradable nanoparticles optimized for treating the posterior eye segment.^[50] Thermosensitive *in situ* gels undergo a phase change induced by temperature, allowing them to form semisolid gels at body temperature to deliver drugs. This feature is applied in biomedicine, employing the change of temperature to control drug release. Poloxamers, are triblock copolymers of polyethyleneoxy-polypropyleneoxy-polyethyleneoxy (PEO-PPO-PEO), which self-assemble as micelles in solution.^[51,52]

7. IMPORTANCE OF IN-SITU GELLING SYSTEM

In-situ gels promote the controlled and sustained release of the drug because of its special 'Sol-Gel transition.' after administration. Because of the sustained release of drug frequency of drug administration and the dose of a drug can be reduced. Accuracy of dosing and controlled release of drugs from in-situ gels results in no drug accumulation and no side effects. Significant increases in bioavailability and reduction in dose of a drug. The increased residence time of the drug and increased contact of the drug with tissue due to gel formation. Accurate and reproducible doses delivery is possible with in situ gels unlike conventional gel formulations. In-situ gel systems show ease of administration because of their physical form which results in improving patient compliance and comfort.^[53]

8. APPROACHES OF IN-SITU GEL DRUG DELIVERY

There are three broadly defined mechanisms used for triggering the in-situ gel formation: Physiological stimuli, physical changes in biomaterials, and chemical reactions. In-situ formation based on physical mechanism: Diffusion: Diffusion is the type of physical approach used in in-situ gel formulations. This method involves the release/ diffusion of solvent from a polymer solution to surrounding tissue resulting in Precipitation or Coagulation of polymer matrix. Swelling: In-situ formation can also occur when a material absorbs water from the surrounding environment and expand to occur desired space. In this method, the polymer absorbs surrounding fluids that are present in the exterior environment

and swell to release the drug slowly. In-situ formation based on physiological stimuli: Thermally triggered system: Temperature-sensitive hydrogels are probably the foremost commonly studied class of environment-sensitive polymer systems in drug formulation development.^[54] The use of polymers, where the transition from sol-gel is caused by increased temperature, is an attractive way to approach in-situ formation. The ideal critical temperature range for such systems is ambient and physiological temperatures, facilitating clinical manipulation and requiring no external heat source other than the body to gel the trigger. The useful system must be adjustable to account for small differences in local temperature that may be encountered on the surface of the skin or the appendages in the oral cavity. There are three main strategies for the formation of temperature-responsive sol-gel polymer systems. For convenience, temperature-sensitive hydrogels are classified into negative heat-sensitive, positive heat-sensitive, and heat-reversible gels. Negative temperature-sensitive hydrogels have a low critical solution temperature (LCST) and shrink when heated above the LCST. Polymers with a low critical temperature (LCST) transition between ambient and physiological temperatures are used for this purpose.^[55] One of the most widely studied polymers showing useful LCST transitions is poly N-isopropyl acrylamide (PNIPAAm). Positive temperature-sensitive hydrogels have an upper critical solution temperature (UCST) and such hydrogels shrink when cooled below UCST. The polymer network of polyacrylic acid (PAA) and polyacrylamide (PAAm) or poly acrylamide-co-butyl methacrylate has a positive temperature dependence of swelling. These polymers exhibit miscibility gaps at high or low temperatures and have upper or lower critical solution temperatures. pH triggered systems: In these systems solution to gel transition is triggered by pH change.^[56]

9. ANATOMY AND FUNCTION OF THE EYE

An eye is a spherical structure with a wall made up of three layers: the outer part sclera, the middle parts choroid layer, ciliary body and iris and the inner section nervous tissue layer retina. The sclera is tough fibrous coating that protecting the inner tissues of eye which is white except for the transparent area at the front, that is cornea allows light to enter to the eye. The choroid layer, situated in the sclera, contains many blood vessels that modified at front of the eye as pigmented iris the colored part of the eye (blue, green, brown, hazel, or grey). The main barrier of drug absorption into the eye is the corneal epithelium, in comparison to many other epithelial tissues (intestinal, nasal, bronchial, and tracheal) that is relatively impermeable. The epithelium is squamous stratified, (5-6 layer of cells) with thickness of around 50-100 μm . The basal cells are packed with a tight junction forming not

only an effective barrier to dust particle and most microorganisms, and also for drug absorption. The transcellular or paracellular pathway is the main pathway to penetrate drug across the corneal epithelium. The lipophilic drugs choose the transcellular route whereas the hydrophilic one chooses paracellular pathway for penetration (passive or altered diffusion through intercellular spaces of the cells).^[57]

Fig. 2: Anatomy of the eye.

10. OCULAR ABSORPTION OF DRUG

The common method of ocular drug delivery is topical administration of ophthalmic dosage formulation drops into the lower cul-de-sac. Eye drops outflow quickly due to the eye blinking reflex, and the precorneal region returns to maintain resident volume of around 7 μ l. The available concentration of drug in precorneal fluid provides the driving force for passive transport of drug across the cornea. However, the epithelium is the predominant rate limiting barrier for hydrophilic drugs and where as stroma is rate limiting step for most of the lipophilic drugs. The molecules up to 20,000 Da can cross the conjunctiva, while the molecules up to 5,000 Da can cross the cornea. The human conjunctiva shows 2-30 times more permeable for drugs than cornea and also loss of drug by this route is a major path for drug clearance. A thin fluid layer is covering the exposed part of the eye called as precorneal tear film. The film thickness is about 3–10 mm depending on the measurement method with the resident volume approximately 10 μ l. The osmolality of the tear fluid is approx. 310–350 m Osm/kg in normal eyes and is maintained by the monovalent and divalent inorganic ions

present in fluid such as Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, HCO₃⁻, and proteins. The mean pH of normal tears is about 7.4. Diurnal patterns change the pH of tear, which is a general shift from acid to alkaline during the day. The buffer capacity of the tears fluid is determined by bicarbonate ions, proteins, and mucin.^[58] Tears exhibit a non-Newtonian rheological behavior with viscosity is about 3 m Pas. The mean surface tension of tear film value is approximately 44 m N/m.^[59]

Fig. 3: Absorption routes of a topically applied ophthalmic drug.

11. OCULAR SUSTAINED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

In the novel drug delivery system various approaches like In situ gelling, use of mucoadhesive polymers, polymer coated Nanoparticles and Liposomal formulations are used. These delivery systems delay the elimination of active ingredient from eye and also improve corneal penetration of drug molecule.

11.1 Liposomes

Liposomes are biocompatible and biodegradable lipid vesicles made up of natural lipids and about 25–10 000 nm in diameter. They are having an intimate contact with the corneal and conjunctival surfaces which is desirable for drugs that are poorly absorbed, the drugs with low partition coefficient, poor solubility or those with medium to high molecular weights and

thus increases the probability of ocular drug absorption. The corneal epithelium is thinly coated with negatively charged mucin to which the positive charged surface of the liposomes may bind. Roopal Jain *et al.*; formulated and evaluated soft contact lenses coated with ciprofloxacin entrapped in liposomes. Ciprofloxacin released from the liposomes coated on contact lens inhibited the *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Approximately 40% of the Ciprofloxacin was retained up to three months.^[60]

11.2 Niosomes

Niosomes are non-ionic surfactant vesicles that have potential applications in the delivery of hydrophobic or amphiphilic drugs. Niosomes are developed as they are chemically stable as compared to liposomes, non toxic and do not require special handling techniques. Ghada Abdelbary *et al.*; investigated the feasibility of using non-ionic surfactant vesicles (niosomes) as carriers for the ophthalmic controlled delivery of a water soluble local antibiotic; gentamicin sulphate. They showed a substantial change in the release rate and an alteration in the % EE of gentamicin sulphate from niosomal formulations upon varying type of surfactant, cholesterol content.^[61]

11.3 Implants

For chronic ocular diseases like cytomegalovirus (CMV) retinitis, implants are effective drug delivery system. Earlier non biodegradable polymers were used but they needed surgical procedures for insertion and removal. Presently biodegradable polymers such as Poly Lactic Acid (PLA) are safe and effective to deliver drugs in the vitreous cavity and show no toxic signs. Intravitreal implants of Fluocinolone acetonide were developed for the treatment of posterior segment and reported to control the ocular inflammation of retina.^[62]

11.4 Dendrimers

Dendrimers are large and complex molecules with well defined chemical structure. Dendrimers can successfully used for different routes of drug administration and have reported to have better watersolubility, bioavailability and biocompatibility. The residence time was longer for the solutions containing dendrimers with carboxylic and hydroxyl surface groups. Vandamme *et al.*,^[7] developed and evaluated poly (amidoamine) dendrimers containing fluorescein for controlled ocular drug delivery and determined the influence of size, molecular weight and number of amine, carboxylate and hydroxyl surface groups in several series of dendrimers. The residence time was longer for the solutions containing dendrimers with carboxylic and hydroxyl surface groups.^[63]

11.5 Micro emulsion

Micro emulsion is dispersion of water and oil stabilized using surfactant and co-surfactant to reduce interfacial tension and usually characterized by small droplet size 100 nm, higher thermodynamic stability and clear appearance. Selection of aqueous phase, organic phase and surfactant/co-surfactant systems are critical parameters which can affect stability of the system. Vandamme *et al.*; reported optimization of these components results in significant improvement in solubility of the drug molecule e.g. Indomethacin, Chloramphenicol for eye diseases.^[64]

11.6 Nanosuspensions

Nanosuspensions have emerged as a promising strategy for the efficient delivery of hydrophobic drugs because they enhanced not only the rate and extent of ophthalmic drug absorption but also the intensity of drug action with significant extended duration of drug effect. For commercial preparation of nanosuspensions, techniques like media milling and high-pressure homogenization have been used. Pingatello *et al.*; formulated nanosuspension of Flurbiprofen using Eudragit RS 100. The higher drug level in the aqueous humor was reported using Eudragit RS 100 nanosuspensions for the ophthalmic controlled delivery of ibuprofen.^[65]

12. Mechanism of Sol-Gel Formulation

In situ forming hydrogels are liquid preparations upon instillation undergoing phase transition in the ocular cul-de-sac to form viscoelastic gel and this provides a response to environmental changes. In situ gel forming ophthalmic drug delivery systems prepared from polymers that exhibit reversible phase transitions (sol–gel–sol) and pseudo plastic behavior to minimize interference with blinking. Such a system can be formulated as a liquid dosage form suitable to be administered by instillation into the eye which, upon exposure to physiological conditions, changes to the gel phase, thus increasing the pre-corneal residence time of the delivery system. The vast majority of the In situ forming drug delivery systems reported is based on polymeric materials which forms gel matrices upon administration. Polymers that have been investigated includes^[66], polysaccharides like alginate, gellan and xyloglucan, polyesters like PLA and PLGA polyethers like PEG-PPG-PEG (Poloxamers), or mixed polyesters and polyether's such as PEG-PLGAPEG.^[67]

13. EVALUATIONS OF INSITU GEL SYSTEM

Evaluation parameters for insitu gel formulations includes clarity, pH measurement, gelling capacity, drug content, rheological study, in vitro diffusion study, isotonicity, antibacterial activity, in vivo ocular testing in rabbits and accelerated stability studies. The formulation should have an optimum viscosity that will allow for easy instillation into the eye as a liquid (drops), which would undergo a rapid sol-to-gel transition (triggered by pH, temperature or ion exchange).

13.1 Physical parameters

Physical parameters to be tested for insitu gel solution are clarity, pH, gelling capacity, and drug content estimation.

13.2 Gelling capacity

The gelling capacity of the prepared formulation is determined by placing a drop of the formulation in a vial containing 2.0 ml of freshly prepared simulated tear fluid and visually observe.

13.3 Rheological studies

The viscosity measurements can be calculated using Brookfield viscometer, Cone and Plate viscometer. In-situ gel formulation is placed in sample tube. Formulation should have viscosity of 5-1000 m Pas, before gelling & after formation of gel should have viscosity from about 50-50,000 m Pas.

13.4 In vitro drug release studies

In vitro release study of insitu gel solution is carried out by using Franz diffusion cell. The best fit model is check for Krosmeyers Peppas and Fickinian diffusion mechanism for their kinetics.^[68]

13.5 Texture analysis

The consistency, firmness and cohesiveness of insitu gel are assessed by using texture profile analyzer which mainly indicated gel strength and easiness in administration in vivo. Higher values of adhesiveness of gels are needed to maintain an intimate contact with mucus surface.

13.6 Isotonicity evaluation

Isotonicity is important characteristic of the ophthalmic preparations. Isotonicity has to be maintained to prevent tissue damage or irritation of eye. All ophthalmic preparations are

subjected to isotonicity testing, since they exhibited good release characteristics and gelling capacity and the requisite viscosity.

13.7 Drug-polymer interaction study and thermal analysis

Interaction study should be performed with Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopy. During gelation process the nature of the interacting forces can be evaluated using the technique by employing KBr pellet method. Thermo gravimetric Analysis (TGA) can be conducted for in situ forming polymeric system to quantitate the percentage of water in hydrogel. Differential Scanning calorimetry (DSC) conducted to observe if there are any changes in thermo grams as compared with pure active ingredients used for gelation.

13.8 Antibacterial activity

The microbiological growth of bacteria is measured by concentration of antibiotics and this has to be compared with that produced by known concentration of standard preparation of antibiotic.

13.9 Ocular irritancy test

The Draize irritancy test should be designed for the ocular irritation potential of the ophthalmic product prior to marketing. According to the Draize test, the amount of substance applied to the eye is normally 100µl placed into the lower culdesac with observation of the various criteria made at a designed required time interval of 1hr, 24hrs, 48 hrs, 72hrs, and 1week after administration. Three rabbits (male) weighing 1.5 to 2kg are used for the study. The sterile formulation is instilled twice a day for a period of 7 days, and a cross-over study is carried out (a 3 day washing period with saline was carried out before the cross-over study). Rabbits are observed periodically for redness, swelling, watering of the eye.^[69]

13.10 Clarity

The clarity of the formulations before and after gelling is often determined by visual examination of the formulations under light alternatively against white and black backgrounds. Additionally, the contents are often set in motion with a swirling action. Also, it is observed for the formation of turbidity or any unwanted particles dispersed within the solution.

13.11 pH

pH affects both the solubility and stability of the drug in the formulation. The formulation should remain stable at its pH and at the same time be non-irritating to the patient at the time of administration. The pH is measured by a digital pH meter. It should be pre-calibrated using standard buffers of pH 4 and pH 7 according to established procedures.

13.12 Gelling capacity

Gelling capacity is determined for in-situ gels for ophthalmic formulations. The in-situ gel is mixed with simulated tear fluid to examine the gelling ability of ophthalmic products. This is determined by visual observation of a drop of formulation during a vial containing 2.0 ml of freshly prepared simulated tear fluid. Gelation was visually assessed by recording the time and time it took for the formed gel to dissolve.

13.13 Gelation PH

Gelation pH is determined by an in-situ gel formation system incorporating a pH-sensitive polymer. The formulation is then placed in a beaker and 1M NaOH was added dropwise with continuous stirring. Use a pH meter (Equiptronics digital pH meter) to check the pH and while the viscosity is also measured. Changes in viscosity at each pH are recorded. The pH at which a rapid change in viscosity is observed is referred to as gelation PH.

14. MECHANISM OF *IN SITU* GELS

The mechanism of *in situ* gels is based on following mechanisms:

14.1 Swelling

In this method of *in-situ* gel formation the material absorbs water from its surroundings and expands to fill the necessary space. Glycerol monooleate, for example, is a polar lipid that expands in water and forms lyotropic liquid crystalline phase structures. It has some bio adhesive qualities and is enzymatically destroyed *in vivo*.

14.2 Diffusion

In this procedure, the solvent from the polymer solution diffuses into the surrounding tissue which the polymer matrix precipitates or solidifies as a result. The solvent N-Methyl Pyrrolidone (NMP) has been proven to have effect in such a system.

14.3 Based on the mechanics of chemical reactions

Precipitation of inorganic solids from supersaturated ionic solutions, enzymatic activities and photo-initiated processes are all examples of chemical reactions that result in *in situ* gelation.^[70,71,72,73]

a) Ionic cross linking

Polymers may undergo phase transition in existence of several ions. Some of the polysaccharides fall into the class of Ion-sensitive ones.²⁰ While k-carrageenan forms rigid, fragile gels in account of small amount of K⁺, i-carrageenan forms flexible gels mainly in the presence of Ca²⁺. Gellan gum economically available as Gelrite® is an anionic polysaccharide that goes through *in situ* gelling in the presence of mono and divalent cations, including Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺ and Na⁺. Gelation of the low methoxy pectins can be caused by divalent cations that are Ca²⁺. Likewise alginic acid goes through gelation in presence of divalent/polyvalent cations. Example Ca²⁺ due to the contact with gluronic acid block in alginate chains.

b) Enzymatic cross linking

In Situ formation catalysed by natural enzymes has not been considered widely but appears to have some advantages over chemical and photochemical approaches. For example, an enzymatic process works efficiently under physiologic conditions without need for potentially harmful chemicals such as monomers and initiators.

c) Photo polymerization

Photo-polymerisation is commonly used for *in situ* formation of biomaterials. A solution of reactive macromer and initiator can be injected into a tissues site and the use of electromagnetic radiation to form gel. Acrylate or related polymerizable functional groups are normally used as the individual monomers and macromers because they rapidly undergo photo-polymerisation in the existence of suitable photo initiator. Typically long ultraviolet and visible wavelengths are used. Short wavelength ultraviolet is not used often because it has partial penetration of tissue and biologically harmful. A ketone such as 2,2 dimethoxy-2-phenyl acetophenone, is often used as the initiator for ultraviolet photo-polymerization while camphor quinone and ethyl eosin initiators are often used in visible light systems.^[74]

15. Importance of in situ gelling system

- 1) In-situ gel helps for the controlled and sustained release of the drugs by its “Sol-Gel” transition.
- 2) It helps in reducing frequency of drug administration in the body.
- 3) Low doses of the drugs are required and there will be no drug accumulation and side effects.
- 4) It increases bioavailability of drugs.
- 5) Residence time of drug will be increased due to gel formation.
- 6) The in-situ gel drug delivery system decreases wastage of the drug.^[75]

16. Ideal characteristics

- 1) It should be biocompatible.
- 2) It is capable of adhering to the mucus membrane.
- 3) Preferred pseudo plastic behavior of polymer.
- 4) Good tolerance and optical clarity is more preferred.
- 5) It should influence the tear behavior.
- 6) The polymer should be capable of decreasing the viscosity with increasing shear rate.^[76]

CONCLUSION

Ophthalmic delivery systems that gel in place can better treat diseases of the anterior segment of the eye and may be used to create a number of APIs. In the rapidly developing field of ocular medication delivery, most researchers are taking on challenges to address a variety of issues related to this delivery. Continuous technological advancements and steady progress in our understanding of the laws and mechanisms governing the uptake and elimination of drugs into the eye have undoubtedly improved the efficacy of ophthalmic delivery systems. *in situ* gel technology for ocular medication delivery may reduce the shortcomings of current drug delivery systems. *In situ* gels improve bioavailability, prolong drug release, and reduce dose frequency. Benefits boost patient acceptance and clinical outcomes. The development and use of *in situ* gel systems mark a significant advancement in ocular drug delivery, offering a promising solution to challenges associated with conventional topical treatments. These gels, designed intelligently with responsive properties, extend contact time on the eye's surface, and enable sustained drug release, thereby enhancing bioavailability and in turn therapeutic effectiveness. Additionally, incorporating nanotechnology-based drug carriers further improves treatment.

REFERENCE

1. Ashim KM. Ophthalmic drug delivery system. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc., 1993; 58: 105-10.
2. Kaur IP, Garg A, Singla AK, Aggarwal D. Vesicular systems in ocular drug delivery an overview. *Int J Pharm.*, 2004; 269: 1-14.
3. Singh SK, Bandyopadhyay P. Pharmacia Corporation. Ophthalmic formulation with novel gum composition. US., 2006; 7128928.
4. Thorsteinn L, Tomi J. Cyclodextrins in ocular drug delivery. *Adv Drug Del Rev.*, 1999; 36: 59-78.
5. Srividya B, Cardoza RM, Amin PD. Sustain ophthalmic delivery of ofloxacin from a pH triggered in situ gelling system. *J Control Rel.*, 2001; 73: 205–211. doi: 10.1016/S0168-3659(01)00279-6.
6. Bhowmik M, Bain MK, Ghosh LK, Chattopadhyay D. Effect of Salts on Gelation and Drug Release Profiles of Methylcellulose Based Ophthalmic Thermo-reversible in-situ Gels. *Pharm Dev Technol.* doi: 10.3109/10837451003774369. in press.
7. Schoenwald RD. Ocular drug delivery: pharmacokinetic considerations. *Clin Pharmacokinet*, 1990; 18: 255–269. doi: 10.2165/00003088-199018040-00001.
8. Hongyi Q, Wenwen C, Chunyan H, Li L, Chuming C, Wenmin L, Chunjie W. Development of a poloxamer analogs/carbopol-based in-situ gelling and mucoadhesive ophthalmic delivery system for puerarin. *Int J Pharm.*, 2007; 337: 178–187. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2006.12.038.
9. Ridell A, Evertsson H, Nilsson S, Sundelof LO. Amphiphilic association of ibuprofen and two non ionic cellulose derivatives in aqueous solution. *J Pharm Sci.*, 1999; 88: 1175–1181. doi: 10.1021/js990092u.
10. Bain MK, Bhowmik M, Maity D, Bera NK, Ghosh SN, Chattopadhyay D. Control of Thermo Reversible Gelation of Methylcellulose Using Different Molecular Weight of PEG & NaCl for Sustain Delivery of Ophthalmic Drug. *J Appl Polym Sci.*, 2010; 118: 631–637. doi: 10.1002/app.32350.
11. Hsiue GH, Chang RW, Wang CH, Lee SH. Development of in situ thermosensitive drug vehicles for glaucoma therapy. *Biomaterials.*, 2003; 24: 2423–2430. doi: 10.1016/S0142-9612(03)00035-8
12. Jeong B, Choi YK, Bae YH, Zentner G, Kim SW. New biodegradable polymers for injectable drug delivery systems. *J Control Rel.*, 1999; 62: 109–114. doi: 10.1016/S0168-3659(99)00061-9

13. Qiu Y, Park K. Environmentally-sensitive polymer hydrogels. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.*, 2001; 53: 321–339. doi: 10.1016/S0169-409X(01)00203-
14. Gaudana, R.; Ananthula, H.K.; Parenky, A.; Mitra, A.K. Ocular Drug Delivery. *AAPS J.*, 2010; 12: 348–360.
15. Jumelle, C.; Gholizadeh, S.; Annabi, N.; Dana, R. Advances and Limitations of Drug Delivery Systems Formulated as Eye Drops. *J. Control. Release*, 2020; 321: 1–22.
16. Mofidfar, M.; Abdi, B.; Ahadian, S.; Mostafavi, E.; Desai, T.A.; Abbasi, F.; Sun, Y.; Manche, E.E.; Ta, C.N.; Flowers, C.W. Drug Delivery to the Anterior Segment of the Eye: A Review of Current and Future Treatment Strategies. *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2021; 607: 120924
17. Xu Y, Wang C, Tam KC, Li L. Salt-assisted and salt-suppressed sol-gel transitions of methylcellulose in water. *Langmuir.*, 2004; 20: 646–652. doi: 10.1021/la0356295.
18. Mahesh NS, Manjula BP. Study of an Alginate /HPMC based in situ gelling ophthalmic delivery system for levofloxacin hydrochloride. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2012; 4(3): 655-8.
19. Shankar SJ, Kalikonda A. pH induced insitu gel formulation of Lomefloxacin HCl. *Universal Journal of Pharmacy*, 2014; 3(1): 38-43.
20. Thorsteinn L, Tomi J. Cyclodextrins in ocular drug delivery. *Adv Drug Del Rev.*, 1999; 36: 59-78.
21. Gokulgandhi MR, Parikh JR, Megha Barot M, Modi DM. A pH triggered in situ gel forming ophthalmic drug delivery system for tropicamide. *Drug Delivery Technology*, 2007; 5: 44-9.
22. Zhidong L, Jiawei L, Shufang N, Hui L, Pingtian D, Weisan P. Study of an alginate/HPMC based in situ gelling ophthalmic delivery system for gatifloxacin. *Int J Pharm.*, 2006; 315: 12-7.
23. Saxena P, Kushwaha SK. Temperature sensitive ophthalmic hydrogels of levofloxacin hemihydrate with enhanced solubility and prolonged retention time. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2013; 5(3): 77-883.
24. Viram P, Lumbhani AN. Development and evaluation of ion-dependent insitu nasal gelling systems of metoclopramide hydrochloride as an antimigraine model drug. *International Journal of Latest Research in Science and Technology*, 2012; 1(2): 80-9.
25. Vodithala S, Khattry S, Shastri N, Sadanandam M. Development and evaluation of Thermoreversible Ocular Gels Of ketorolac tromethamine. *International Journal of Biopharmaceutics*, 2010; 1(1): 39-45.

26. Varshosaz J, Tabbakhian M, Salmani Z. Designing of a Thermosensitive Chitosan/Ploxamer insitu Gel for Ocular Delivery of Ciprofloxacin. *The Open Drug Delivery Journal*, 2008; 2(1): 61-70.
27. Thorsteinn L, Tomi J. Cyclodextrins in ocular drug delivery. *Adv Drug Del Rev.*, 1999; 36: 59–78.
28. Gokulgandhi MR, Parikh JR, Megha Barot M, Modi DM. A pH triggered in situ gel forming ophthalmic drug delivery system for tropicamide. *Drug Delivery Technology*, 2007; 5: 44–9.
29. Zhidong L, Jiawei L, Shufang N, Hui L, Pingtian D, Weisan P. Study of an alginate/HPMC based in situ gelling ophthalmic delivery system for gatifloxacin. *Int J Pharm.*, 2006; 315: 12–7. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2006.01.029.
30. Indu PK, Manjit S, Meenakshi K. Formulation and evaluation of ophthalmic preparations of acetazolamide. *Int J Pharm.*, 2000; 199: 119–27. doi: 10.1016/s0378-5173(00)00359-8
31. Katarina E, Johan C, Roger P. Rheological evaluation of poloxamer as an in situ gel for ophthalmic use. *Eur J Pharm Sci.*, 1998; 6: 105–12. doi: 10.1016/s0928-0987(97)00075-4
32. Kumaran KS, Karthika K, Padmapreetha J. Comparative review on conventional and advanced ocular drug delivery formulations. *Int. J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2010; 2(4): 1-5.
33. Kaur IP, Singh M, Kanwar M. Formulation and evaluation of ophthalmic preparations of acetazolamide. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, Apr. 20, 2000; 199(2): 119-27.
34. Rathore KS, Nema RK. Formulation and evaluation of ophthalmic films for timolol maleate. *Planta indica*, 2008; 4: 49-50.
35. Gurny R, Ibrahim H, Buri P. The development and use of in situ formed gels, triggered by pH. *Biopharmaceutics of ocular drug delivery*, 1993; 81-90.
36. Kondepati HV, Kulyadi GP, Tippavajhala VK. A Review on In-situGel Forming Ophthalmic Drug Delivery Systems. *Res J Pharm Tech.*, 2018; 11(1): 380–6.
37. J.B. Mueller et al. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0733862707001241> *Emerg. Med. Clin. North Am.*, 2008.
38. Y. Shirasaki <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022354916326211J>. *Pharm. Sci.*, 2008.
39. I.P. Kaur *et al.* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378517302004386> *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2002.
40. C. Jumelle *et al* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168365920300778>. *J. Control. Release*, 2020.

41. K.S. Vellonen *et al.* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168365914004532> J. Control. Release, 2014.
42. M. Bhowmik *et al.* Effect of xanthan gum and guar gum on in situ gelling ophthalmic drug delivery system based on poloxamer-407 Int. J. Biol. Macromol, 2013.
43. K. Ravishankar *et al.* Advances in chitosan-based hydrogels: evolution from covalently crosslinked systems to ionotropically crosslinked superabsorbents React. Funct. Polym. 2020.
44. D.Y. Ko *et al.* Recent progress of in situ formed gels for biomedical applications Prog. Polym. Sci., 2013.
45. S. Das *et al.* Imaging methods for the assessment of a complex hydrogel as an ocular drug delivery system for glaucoma treatment: opportunities and challenges in preclinical evaluation Mol. Pharm., 2022.
46. D.Y. Ko *et al.* Recent progress of in situ formed gels for biomedical applications Prog. Polym. Sci., 2013.
47. S. Das *et al.* Imaging methods for the assessment of a complex hydrogel as an ocular drug delivery system for glaucoma treatment: opportunities and challenges in preclinical evaluation Mol. Pharm. (2022)
48. A.D. Permana *et al.* Thermosensitive and mucoadhesive *in situ* ocular gel for effective local delivery and antifungal activity of itraconazole nanocrystal in the treatment of fungal keratitis Int. J. Pharm., 2021.
49. M. Dewan *et al.* Effect of methyl cellulose on gelation behavior and drug release from poloxamer based ophthalmic formulations Int. J. Biol. Macromol, 2015.
49. S.A. Algharib *et al.* Preparation of chitosan nanoparticles by ionotropic gelation technique: effects of formulation parameters and in vitro characterization J. Mol. Struct., 2022.
50. J. Guan *et al.* Optimized preparation of levofloxacin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles by ionotropic gelation Phys. Procedia, 2011.
51. M.V. Dias-Souza *et al.* Comparative study of free and liposome-entrapped chloramphenicol against biofilms of potentially pathogenic bacteria isolated from cooling towers Saudi Pharmaceut. J., 2017.
52. Addo E, Bamiro OA, Siwale R. Anatomy of the eye and common diseases affecting the eye. In: Addo RT, editor. Ocular drug delivery: Advances, challenges and applications, 2016; 11–25.

53. Joseph RR, Venkatraman SS. Drug delivery to the eye: what benefits do nanocarriers offer. *Nanomedicine (Lond)*, 2017; 12(6): 683–702. doi: 10.2217/nnm-2016-0379.[DOI]
54. Zhu M, Wang J, Li N. A novel thermo-sensitive hydrogel-based on poly(N-isopropylacrylamide)/ hyaluronic acid of ketoconazole for ophthalmic delivery. *Artif Cells Nanomed Biotechnol*, 2017. doi: 10.1080/21691401.2017.1368024.[DOI]
55. Bisht R, Mandal A, Jaiswal JK, Rupenthal ID. Nanocarrier mediated retinal drug delivery overcoming ocular barriers to treat posterior eye diseases. *WIREs Nanomed Nanobiotechnol*, 2018. doi: 10.1002/wnan.1473.
56. Jitendra PK, Sharma A, Banik, Dixit S; A new trend ocular drug delivery system. *International. Journal. Of Pharmaceutical. Sciences*, 2011; 2(3): 720-744.
57. Varshosaz J, Tabbakhian M, Salmani Z; Designing of a Thermo sensitive Chitosan/Ploxamer In Situ Gel for Ocular Delivery of Ciprofloxacin; *The Open Drug Delivery Journal*, 2008; 2: 61-70.
58. Nagyova B, Tiffany JM; Components responsible for the surface tension of human tears; *Current Eye Research*, 1999; 19(1): 4-11.
59. Jain R, Shastri P; Study of ocular drug delivery system using drug loaded liposomes; *International. Journal. Of Pharmaceutical. Science Investigation*, 2011; 1(1): 234-244.
60. Abdelbary G; Niosome-Encapsulated Gentamicin for Ophthalmic Controlled Delivery; *AAPS Pharm Sci Tech*, 2008; 9(3): 740–747.
61. Taban M, Lowder C, Kaiser Y; Outcome of Fluocinolone acetonide implant reimplantation for chronic non-infectious posterior uveitis; *Retina*, 2008; 2(8): 1280–1288.
62. Vandamme TF, Brobeck L; Poly(amidoamine) dendrimers as ophthalmic vehicles for ocular delivery of pilocarpine nitrate and tropic amide; *Journal of Control Release*, 2005; 102: 23- 38.
63. Vandamme TF; Micro emulsions as ocular drug delivery systems: recent development and future challenges; *Progress in Retinal and Eye Research*, 2002; 21: 15–34.
64. Pignatello R; Flurbiprofen-loaded acrylate polymer nano suspensions for ophthalmic application; *Biomaterials*, 2002; 23: 3247- 3255.
65. Kamel A.; In vitro and in vivo evaluation of Pluronic F127- based ocular delivery system for timolol maleate; *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 2002; 24(1): 47–55.
66. Peppas NA, Langer R; New challenges in biomaterials; *Science*, 1994; 263(154): 1715- 1720.

67. Ravindra Reddy K, Ravi Shankar Yadav M, Sabitha Reddy P; Preparation and evaluation of Aceclofenac ophthalmic In situ gels; Journal of Chemical, Biological and Physical Sciences, 2011; 1(2): 289-298.
68. Katariya dhirajkumar champalal, Poddar Sushilkumar S; Current status of ophthalmic insitu forming hydrogel. International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences, 2012; 3(3): 372- 388.
69. Li J, Liu H, Liu LL, et al. Chem Pharm Bull., 2014; 62(10): 1000-1008. [Crossref] [Google Scholar] [PubMed]
70. Morsi N, Ghorab D, Refai H, et al. Int J Pharm., 2016; 506(1-2): 57-67. [Crossref] [Google Scholar] [PubMed]
71. Al Khateb K, Ozhmukhametova EK, Mussin MN, et al. Int J Pharm., 2016; 502(1-2): 70-79. [Crossref] [Google Scholar] [PubMed]
72. Qian Y, Wang F, Li R, Zhang Q, Xu Q. Drug Dev Ind Pharm., 2010; 36(11): 1340-1347. [Crossref] [Google Scholar] [PubMed]
73. Mayuri R. Khule, et.al, A Review: in-situ Gel Drug Delivery System, International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), March 2021; 9(3).
74. Ramanjit Saini, et.al, In Situ Gels- A new trends in Ophthalmic drug delivery system , International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research (IJPSR), May 2015; 6(05).
75. Garge Lajri, et.al, Ophthalmic pH Sensitive In-Situ Gel: A Review, Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics, ISSN: 2250-1177.